

An assessment of managerial competency needs: Empirical evidence from a Sri Lankan telecommunication service provider

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Abstract

From the management development viewpoint, it is important to know whether managers possess the required competencies to achieve successful job performance. This could be identified by exploring the competency needs. The aim of the paper is to present and discuss results of an empirical investigation on managerial competency needs using quantitative methodology. The study is confined to a fully integrated telecommunication service provider; 198 managerial employees participated in the survey. The findings led to identify perceived levels of current competency expertise, current and future competency gaps and competencies that managers wish to improve at present and in near future. Managerial implications, limitations and directions for future research are discussed.

Key words- competencies, competency gaps, competency needs, telecommunication industry, Sri Lanka.

Introduction

The world of work has changed radically in many organizations over the past twenty years. Organizations are flatter; some levels of management have been eliminated. Increased focus on the customer and rapid response to problems and opportunities in a continuously changing environment has made the manager a vital resource in guiding and directing front-line workers to success. Managers focus on issues that occurred within their organization; increasingly, they focus on issues that involve a number of organizational entities or that cut across an entire enterprise. To do this, they must manage laterally and up as well as down (Hay Group, 2001). In this context, for a sustained personal development, an expansion of a person's capacity to be effective in managerial roles becomes vital (Brownell and Goldsmith,

2006; Jackson et al., 2003; Tubbs and Schulz, 2006). In this regard, the competency approach marks a new development.

A competency is a measurable characteristic that can be defined in terms of ability and willingness to do a task, generic knowledge, motive, trait, social role, or skill of a person that is related to effective performance in a specific job, organization, or culture (Hay Group, 2001; Hayes, 1979). Organisations adopting a competency approach must create or utilise a competency framework, at minimum a simple list or catalogue, specifying desirable competencies (Markus et al., 2005). Competency frameworks are used in the organizational context to guide decision-making in several areas. For instance, competency gap analysis can identify the needed competencies by a job role, project, or organizational strategy. Once competency gaps were identified, if necessary, appropriate strategies could be taken to eliminate those gaps. Further, competencies can be used as the foundation on which an organization aligns individual careers (Draganidis and Mentzas, 2006; Rothwell and Wellins, 2004; Rowe, 1995; Schippmann et al., 2000). Therefore, a competency framework helps align the HR system vertically with the organization's strategic objectives and horizontally with other HR functions, where it provides a tool for selection, performance management, training and development, and career management. Hence, the importance given to competencies in the organizational context is increasing continually (Horton, 2000; Lawler 1994; Matthewman, 1995; Rees and Garnsey, 2003; Valkeavaara, 1998). This is to a large extent driven by business and human resources agendas to deliver business performance by improving the performance of individual managers (Engle et al., 2001; Heffernan and Flood 2000; Kochanski and Ruse, 1996).

Though there is an enormous diversity in the scope of competency studies (Rothwell et al., 1999; Rothwell and Lindholm, 1999), a few competency studies have analyzed the impact of competency-based methodologies on human resource development (HRD). Developing competencies that match job requirements have become an issue in HRD in any context. In many instances, a vague list of desirable competencies provided by policymakers or advocated by scholars is used as a guide in making crucial decisions on HRD programmes (Hansson, 2001). Further, several academic literature propose that competency needs should be identified in terms of gaps or deficits. This is because a gap derives real needs while reducing managers' subjectivity and preference in identifying managerial competency needs. However, a few empirical studies have been conducted treating competency needs as gaps (Barber and Tietje, 2004; Chen et al., 2005; Hansson, 2001). Finally, a limited number of competency studies have been conducted in Asia (see- Chen et al., 2005; Han et al., 2006; Xiao, 2006; Zhu et al., 2000). Therefore, this research aimed to partially fill this lacuna in literature by investigating managerial competency needs in the South Asian context, Sri Lanka in particular. It is expected that this research will contribute to the understanding of effective HRD strategies to address competency needs of managers.

The study was conducted in the telecommunication industry of Sri Lanka.

Telecommunication industry is considered to be one of the fastest growing business sectors of the country; it is facing an increasingly competitive future. To be competitive in the industry firms must produce world-class, quality products and services, design those to meet the specific customer's needs, and deliver them at competitive prices. Managers have always played a critical role in organizations. They work as a team, exhibit creativity, responds to customers, continually improve products and services, and turn policies into action. The impact of outstanding managers on revenues and profits is well-documented. Hence,

competent managers are one of the key assets to outperform competitors. Sri Lankan telecommunication firms are aware of the uncertainty regarding the performance, and the need of survival of the industry and remaining competitive in the future. In the above context, for the study, following research questions were raised: 1. What competencies are perceived to be important for now and near future by the managers? 2. What are the current expertise levels of different work-related competencies of managers? 3. Are there any differences across current competency expertise, current importance, and future importance? If so, what are current and future competency needs in terms of gaps? 4. What are the competencies that managers request to improve at present and in near future? Based on these four research questions the following specific research objectives were developed: 1. To investigate the perceived levels of current competency expertise, current importance and future importance of different work-related competencies, 2. To derive current and future competency needs in terms of gaps, and 3. To evaluate training and development requests of the managers for the present and near future. In order to provide the context for the paper, the next section briefly reviews the theoretical background of the study. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Subsequently, the main findings are presented and discussed. The paper concludes with a discussion on the implications of the findings and research areas for further inquiry and understanding.

Theoretical background

Competency

The term “competency” was first used in the managerial context in the research conducted by Boyatzis (1982) in the late 1970s in the USA to identify the characteristics which distinguish superior from average managerial performance. Boyatzis adopted the term “competency”, plural “competencies”, which he described as an underlying characteristic of an individual

that is causally related to effective or superior performance in a job (Boyatzis, 1982). The study concluded that there was no single factor but a range of factors that differentiated superior from average performers. These included personal characteristics, experience, motives and other attributes. In literature, the term competency is attributed multiple meanings depending on the context and perspective (Garavan and McGuire, 2001; Viitala, 2005). For instance, a "competency" is seen as an input or an output of human behaviour. In the United Kingdom competencies are viewed as outputs: employees display competencies in the degree to which their work meets or exceeds prescribed work standards. In the United States, competencies are seen mainly as inputs: they consist of clusters of knowledge, attitudes and skills that affect an individual's ability to perform (Brophy and Kiely, 2002; Heffernan and Flood, 2000; Stuart and Lindsay, 1997). As each approach has its own strengths, it is suggested that those should be regarded as complementary (Elkin, 1990; Stuart and Lindsay, 1997). In this regard, Stuart and Lindsay (1997) emphasized the need of a comprehensive framework for understanding and working with managerial competencies.

In recent years, one of the emerging themes is that of competencies and their role in helping organizations cope with the changing environment. The competency based approach puts the human being at the centre of attention and underlines the importance of human resources to reach the objectives of the organization (Antonacopoulou and FitzGerald, 1996; Cheng et al., 2003; Heffernan and Flood 2000; Hondegem and Vandermeulen, 2000). Therefore, competencies have become the common language of the human resource system which enables the organization to match its human resources against the resources it needs (Woodruffe, 1991). Competency based approach assist an organization in the identification of skills, knowledge, behaviours and capabilities requested by a project or job role in alignment with the organizational strategies and priorities (Draganidis and Mentzas, 2006). In this

regard, the key integrative concept has been that of occupational competence, especially managerial competence. The underlying thrust here has been the recognition that organizational effectiveness is in part related to the performance of the organization's managers, a conception given some support by the research conducted by Boyatzis (1982). Therefore, given the discussion above, by managerial competency in this study is meant input measures in the manner suggested by Boyatzis (1982) and Spencer and Spencer (1993) rather than outputs. As the findings of this study could have individual development focus, the definition given by Hay Group (2001) was used, i.e., competency is a measurable characteristic of a person that is related to effective performance in a specific job, organization or culture. These characteristics are defined in terms of behaviours. Because competencies are behavioural, they can be developed.

The literature identifies two interrelated sets of managerial competencies: technical and generic (Boyatzis, 1982). Technical managerial competencies consist of having the knowledge and skills that enable the manager to give an effective performance in specific areas of management such as marketing. Generic managerial competencies refer to managers' capability of self-regulation and self-control at work (Kanungo and Misra, 1992). It also covers other individual characteristics such as attitudes, motivation, or personality traits that involve coping with less programmed and technical tasks and more generic situations (Agut et al, 2003). Many studies also make a distinction between soft and hard competencies: personality traits were considered as soft and job-specific abilities were considered as hard (Parry, 1996). Several studies have identified lists of relevant managerial competencies, for instance, Boyatzis's (1982) executive level managerial competencies, Spencer and Spencer's (1993) competencies of top performing executives, Byham's (1990) executive level dimensions, Cox and Cooper's (1988) competencies of chief executives, and Kotter's (1982)

general managerial competencies. Literature also emphasises the need of identifying clusters of competencies required to perform various jobs (Parry, 1996). Educational objectives are often categorized into three distinct domains – cognitive, affective and psychomotor. Consistent with this framework, Barber and Tietje (2004) used a knowledge-skill-value (KSV) structure to facilitate the identification of key competencies. The term knowledge was used to represent the cognitive domain, value for the affective, and skill for the psychomotor. Hay Group (2001) identified four managerial competency clusters, namely managing yourself, managing your team, managing the work, and managing collaboratively. However, literature indicates the complexities and ambiguities of managerial work and suggests that the variations in skills, functions and contexts of management roles make a one-size-fits-all competency profile impractical (Hales, 1986; McKenna, 2002; Whitely, 1989).

Competency gaps and means of addressing competency gaps

It is important to identify which particular set of key managerial competencies are required for an organization to achieve its strategic goals. Equally vital is the ability to “health-check” those competencies on a regular basis (Homer, 2001). Therefore, from the HRD viewpoint, it is important to know whether managers possess the required competencies to achieve successful job performance. Further, literature suggests that when competency needs are considered in terms of gaps, it allows for a better understanding of managerial job performance (Agut et al., 2003; Barber and Tietje, 2004; Scholes and Endacott, 2003). A discrepancy or a gap arises when a competency an individual possesses is lower than what is required for the job performance (Agut and Grau, 2002; Boydell and Leary, 1996; Goldstein, 1991; Moore and Dutton, 1978).

However, Antonacopoulou and FitzGerald (1996) state that there is a danger if organizations concentrate on competencies of the past rather than on competencies of tomorrow. Hence, competency framework should reflect an organization's current and future needs (Prahalad and Hamel, 1990). Therefore, in the study a competency deficit or competency need is defined as the gap between the current and required level of a competency for a successful job performance. Though a perceived gap could sometimes be an expression of preference (Latham, 1988), such information is useful in making organizational strategic decisions (Hansson, 2001).

Once competency gaps were identified, if necessary, those could be eliminated through training and development or other measures, such as job enrichment, job content innovation, job redesign, or enhancement of the organizational climate (Bee and Bee, 1994; Goldstein, 1991). However, very often competency management is integrated with learning management systems (Bartram, 2004; Camuffo and Gerli, 2004; Hackett, 2001; Mumford et al., 2000; Naquin and Holton, 2003; Reio and Sutton, 2006). Though this could be criticized because a deficit in competency does not necessarily imply an adoption of a training and development solution, the link between competencies and training and development add tremendous value to users who can immediately see what they need in order to acquire competencies (Homer, 2001; Wright and Geroy, 1992). Therefore, competency-based training and development is seen as an important strategic tool in addressing competency gaps (McClelland, 1994; Jackson et al., 2003). In this research we also consider that to face a continuously changing environment managers' competencies need to be renewed on a regular basis. Therefore, training and development could play a major role in expanding a person's capacity to be effective in managerial roles and processes.

Measurement issues with the competency approach

Despite the increasing popularity of competency frameworks among practitioners, the scientific community has regarded competency studies with some degree of scepticism (Lievens et al., 2004). The validity of “competencies” as measurable constructs appears to be at the core of this controversy (Lawler, 1996; Schippmann et al., 2000; Tett et al., 2000). Content validity means that the list of competencies used for the study is a representative sample of the universe of interest. Face validity means that the competencies are accurate and appropriate as judged by their users. In this regard, Hayes et al. (2000) argue that the lists of competencies will always be incomplete. They cite examples of studies where managers have not been able to describe all the competencies required for a job. Construct validity emphasizes the importance of operationalizing competencies so as to observe and measure (Markus et al., 2005). In criterion validity, the importance of measuring competencies accurately is emphasized. However, the way competencies are operationalized and measured depend on how those will be used. Competencies are usually assessed using three distinct methodologies: self-evaluation that allows the assessment of the improvement and/or decline of competencies over time; third-party evaluation that allows the monitoring and evaluation of the evolution of individual learning/acquisition of competencies; peer evaluation that allows the evaluation of the possession of competencies as perceived by peers (Camuffo and Gerli, 2004; Graham and Tarbell, 2006). However, the assessment of competencies is likely to suffer from reliability problems, such as rater bias (Fletcher, 2001). Therefore, an accurate measurement of competencies is a key issue (Markus et al., 2005).

Method

Measures

To achieve the purpose of the study, the identification of relevant managerial competencies is the foundation. In generating the list of managerial competencies to be considered for the study, the methodologies adopted by recent competency research were studied (such as Agut et al., 2003; Barber and Tietje, 2004; Hackett, 2001; McCredie and Shackleton, 2000; Reio and Sutton, 2006; Tubbs and Schulz, 2006). The literature on the generation of list of competencies reveals that some build their lists drawing from previous research works while some others have developed their own lists following a certain procedure. For the current study, five-step methodology was used to identify competencies that define a successful manager within the telecommunications industry as perceived by industry experts and managers in Sri Lanka. First, a comprehensive list of competencies was created that were taken from competency literature. Second, in order to standardize the terminology of competency items, a list of 107 technical and generic competencies were summarised that are abstracted from various sources in literature. This list was considered as the hypothesized list of competencies. As the third step, a panel of industry experts from the telecommunication industry was consulted to rank the importance of each competency for managers in the telecommunication industry from the hypothesized competency list created. To ensure that the competencies that are going to be required of managers are valid and useful, as the fourth step, a randomly selected team of managers from the telecommunication industry was consulted to rank the importance of each competency for managers in the telecommunication industry from the hypothesized competency list created. It was decided to take the competencies that are consistently rated of great importance by the two panels. Therefore, as the fifth and final step, the initial lists along with the ranks given by the two panels were independently analysed by the two researchers to identify the most important competencies and to eliminate duplicates. The final list comprised 31 individual competencies and reflected

the absolute minimum number of areas in which capabilities are required for superior performance in a job.

Procedure

There are several means that could be used to derive competency requirements. Yet, by taking into account individuals' perception of how important a specific competency for performing a particular job could avoid an unbalanced focus on less important competencies (Ford and Noe, 1987; Graham and Tarbell, 2006; Guthrie and schwoerer, 1996; Hansson, 2001; Kersh and Evans, 2005). Therefore, self-evaluation method of personal competencies was used in the research as it plays an increasingly prominent role in education and training and development field (Agut et al., 2003; Camuffo and Gerli, 2004; Hayes et al., 2000). The self-administered questionnaire was chosen as the mode for data collection. Competencies were defined simply, as a headline plus a few sample behaviours. The perceived competency levels were assessed at three levels- current expertise, current importance, and future importance. Those were measured as follows:

- **Current competency expertise level:** The five point Likert scale used to establish the level of competencies currently possessed is: 5=Very High, 4=High, 3=Average, 2=Low, 1=Nothing at all. In the current expertise, a respondent estimates his/her competence on each of the 31 competencies.
- **Competency importance for current job:** The five point Likert scale used to establish how important a particular competency in performing his/her current job is: 5=Very High, 4=High, 3=Average, 2=Low, 1=No Need. In current importance, a respondent makes a judgment on how important each of the 31 competencies for the current job performance.

- **Competency importance for future success:** The five point Likert scale used to establish the level of competency importance for future success is: 5=Very High, 4=High, 3=Average, 2=Low, 1=No Need. In future importance, a respondent makes a judgment on how important each of the 31 competencies will be for the future job performance (three years to the future).

Therefore, each of the 510 managers who received a questionnaire was instructed to document perceived levels of current competency expertise, current importance and future importance on each of the 31 work-related competencies. Hence, the procedure adopted in this research allowed not only the possibility of modelling competencies differently but it also generates data that can be used to contrast the individual estimates.

In the research, two competency gaps were established- current and future (see- Agut et al., 2003; Hansson, 2001; Tovey, 1994, 2006).

- **Current competency gap:** The size of the each competency gap was established by measuring the difference between the level of competency currently possessed by respondents and the level of current competency importance. Therefore, the current competency gaps/needs were calculated for each respondent for each of the 31 competencies.
- **Future competency gap:** The size of the each competency gap was established by measuring the difference between the level of current competency importance and the level of competency requirement for future success. Therefore, the future competency gaps/needs were calculated for each respondent for each of the 31 competencies.

Following the criterion proposed by Agut and Grau (2002) and Agut et al. (2003), three types of competency gaps were identified: negative gap (the present competency level is lower than that required: value \leq -.51); adjustment margin (the present competency level is lower but close to that required: $-.5 \leq$ value \leq .5); and positive gap (the present competency level is higher than that required: value \geq .51).

To fulfill the third objective, training and development requests of the individuals' were explored. The terms training and development and competency-based training are used in the study interchangeably because the outcome is the same, i.e., to expand a person's capacity to be effective in managerial roles and processes (Viitala, 2005). The question used was: "Do you need any training and development opportunities to improve your competencies for your current job" and "Do you need any training and development opportunities to improve your competencies for your future success at your current workplace". These dichotomy questions led to emerge two variables ("No, training and development opportunities are not required" and "Yes, training and development opportunities are required") at the two levels- present training and development requests in a competence and future training and development requests in a competence. If respondents indicated that they need training and development opportunities, then another question was asked: "If your answer is 'yes', indicate the most important competencies that you wish to improve" at the current level and future level (up to five answers were possible at each level).

This research is conducted as an independent study of the authors for academic purposes. Therefore, the questions in the questionnaire were designed by the authors and those did not address specific organizational interests. Further, participants were briefed the aims of the study prior to questionnaire distribution and their responses were anonymous. The self-

administered survey questionnaire was pre-tested prior to distribution. The questionnaire's format, length, style, wording and potential duplication were assessed during the pre-test. The pre-tested survey questionnaire after amendments was administered among the respondents as detailed in the section on "the empirical study".

Methods of data analysis

Data analysis was carried out by using the software package for social sciences (SPSS). Descriptive statistics were used to analyze scores of current expertise, current importance, and future importance and also to derive gaps. Paired sample t-test was performed to explore differences between current expertise levels and current and future importance levels to identify the most needed competencies. The McNemar test was carried out to compare present and future training and development requests.

In the attempt to identify the underlying dimensions as perceived by respondents, current and future gaps of the 31 managerial competencies were subjected to exploratory factor analysis (Varimax rotation), separately. Total of six managerial competency clusters for the current level and eight managerial competency clusters for the future level emerged. Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's test statistics were calculated. The KMO statistic for the current level was .931 and for the future level was .806, which were above the customary reference point of 0.5 for a satisfactory factor analysis to proceed. Bartlett's test of sphericity is significant- associated probability for both current and future levels were .000, respectively, which were less than the customary reference point of 0.05 for a satisfactory factor analysis to proceed. The final solutions are summarized in Table 5 and Table 6, which contains factor loadings, factor variance percentages and Cronbach's alpha of the factor.

The empirical study- case company

The study is confined to a fully integrated telecommunication service provider, identified as X Company. It has become the leading company in the industry in Sri Lanka. According to the monthly human resource report as at July 2006, X Company has more than 6,000 employees in total. Specifically, there were 541 managerial level employees, 1026 middle level technical employees, 1279 clerical and aligned employees, 605 call centre employees, 2,232 technical employees, 358 non-technical employees and 290 drivers as the total number of permanent employees. Of the total employees (6331), 2484 attached to headquarter while 3847 attached to regional offices island wide. The average age of the employees is 42.

The 541 managerial level employees of X Company were considered as the population of the study. Of the 541 managerial employees, 510 were contactable during September 2006 when the survey was conducted; some were not contactable as they had left for either official foreign assignments or on leave. The questionnaire was distributed through e-mail or printed form. The questionnaire was voluntarily completed and returned by 203 subjects within 4 weeks of initial questionnaire distribution. A total of 198 usable responses resulted in 39 per cent response rate. The final sample covered all the fields of employment as shown in Table 1. Of the 198 respondents, 70 per cent were males and 30 per cent were females. The mean age was 40 years; 85 per cent married while 15 per cent single. Of the sample, 85 per cent reported having a Bachelors or postgraduate level university education. The current job tenure in X Company was 13 years on average while the current job tenure in X Company in the current field of specialization was 7 years on average. On average, there were 9 subordinates directly reporting each respondent.

Insert Table 1 about here

Results and discussion

Table 2 summarizes the results for the three competency levels. The highest mean values at each level indicate the competencies with highest current expertise, and competencies perceived to be highest importance for now and near future.

Insert Table 2 about here

The results relating to competency needs are summarized in Table 3 along with the results of paired sample t-test. The results of the t-test led to identify the most needed competencies at present and in the near future. For example, the current competency gap of “customer relations knowledge” (-.19) was derived by subtracting current importance of the competency “customer relations knowledge” by current expertise of the competency “customer relations knowledge” (refer Table 2). The future competency gap of “customer relations knowledge” (-.57) was derived by subtracting future importance of the competency “customer relations knowledge” by current importance of the competency “customer relations knowledge” (refer Table 2). The results of the t-test reveal that the differences in mean values are significant for all the constructs. This suggests that managers regard competencies as important for the current business environment, but exhibited greater potential importance of the same in the future. The telecommunication industry is facing an increasingly competitive future. Managers could be aware of the uncertainty regarding the performance and the need of

survival of the industry. Therefore, the results suggest that the managers feel that their company will need to increase all of its competencies across all dimensions in order to remain competitive in the future.

Insert Table 3 about here

To identify whether the gap between, for example, creativity (which was the most highly ranked area needing improvement at current level- refer Table 3) and empathy with people (which was the least often ranked area needing improvement at current level- refer Table 3) is significant, another series of paired sample t-tests could be conducted. Table 4 shows the results of such an analysis. However, the combinations of competencies that could be selected for such an analysis is huge at both current and future levels. Therefore, paired sample t-test was run on few selected competencies at current level. These competencies were selected considering the size of the gap and the type of the gap. The results shown in Table 4 reveal that there is a wider gap for some competencies relative to others at current level.

Insert Table 4 about here

The results of the principal component analysis for managerial competency gaps at the current level and future level are summarized in Table 5 and Table 6, respectively. As that can be seen from Table 5 and Table 6, 31 competency needs were differently clustered for present and for future. Further, though competency clusters are sufficiently internally

consistent, only Competency Cluster 1 showed considerable percentage of variance at present level as well as at future level.

Insert Table 5 about here

Insert Table 6 about here

Table 7 shows the cross-tabulation of training and development requests for now and future. Of the 186 responded, 154 revealed that they need training and development opportunities to improve their present levels of competencies. Of the 186, 162 revealed that they need development opportunities to improve their levels of competencies for future. The result of the McNemar test also shows that managers request training and development opportunities for now as well as for future.

Insert Table 7 about here

Table 8 shows the results of the most important competencies that respondents wish to improve. 154 respondents put forward 489 development requests for the current level while 162 respondents put forward 372 development requests for the future level. That is each respondent requested an average of 3.2 and 2.3 development opportunities for present and for near future, respectively. The majority of the training and development requests are concentrated on the areas of Competency Cluster 6 for present and Competency Cluster 5 for future. Respondents have not requested training and development opportunities in the areas of Competency Cluster 4 for present and Competency Clusters 7 and 8 for future.

Insert Table 8 about here

Concluding remarks and implications

The study identified a list of competencies to a group of managers in a Sri Lankan telecommunication firm. One of the main features of the current study is the usage of self-reporting method to assess competency levels. The each participant was asked to rate his/her own perceived current level of expertise, current importance and future importance of each of the 31 work-related competencies. The responses led to identify individual competency gaps at current level as well as at future level. Further, the study made an attempt to assess the competency needs and the areas of training and development requests. Hence, from a theoretical viewpoint, this study makes a contribution to the analysis of managerial capabilities in terms of competencies. Further, the findings could be used to assist in both organizations and individuals to apply strategic decisions in managing individual careers.

The study is based on an operative method to analyze competency needs in terms of gaps, as the academic literature proposes. When self-reports accurately reflect an individual's levels of competencies and once competency gaps are identified, such gaps could be addressed through the most appropriate strategy, and as a consequence job performance could be improved. However, there could be situations where individuals consistently give higher (or lower) estimates of the importance of the competency as well as higher (or lower) estimates of their own competency. In this regard, the validation of competencies becomes vital as competencies describe normative behaviours, behaviours an organization wishes to promote and develop to enhance organizational effectiveness.

The findings suggested three possible methods of interpreting competency gaps. 1) As differences between individual gap ratings. For example, “creativity showed the highest competency gap at the current level while empathy with people showed the lowest competency gap at the current level” 2) There is a possibility to compare across gap scores. For example, “there is a significant difference in the gap between creativity and empathy with people at the current level”. This might suggest that addressing the wider gap in creativity is more important than addressing the narrow gap in empathy with people 3) The results of the factor analysis led to suggest different collections of competencies. Therefore, if training and development is seen as a possible strategy to address competency needs, it is important to ensure that individual training and development plans are linked to competency requirements of the individuals. In this regard, this gap analysis method of the identification of competency needs could be used to match the competency needs to training and development requests. Such a link between the levels of competencies and training and development requirements add value to users. They could identify what are the important competencies that they should develop and what training and development opportunities are needed in order to develop those required competencies. However, while competency lists may provide useful guidelines for the design of training and development programmes it would be erroneous to assume that either all of the competencies included in a programme will be relevant for all managers or that a manager who develops all of these competencies to a satisfactory standard will be competent to perform a particular managerial role effectively. In this regard, once competency gaps have been identified, organizations have to decide whether there is a real need of addressing each and every competency gap; what would be the cost of ignoring a competency gap?

In the organizational context where resources are scarce, an organization could create a culture where individuals maintain their own personal competency profile along with their personal development plan. In such a context, individuals could be encouraged to develop their personal competency profile benchmarking a job along his/her career path. The outcome of this effort would be beneficial for both the individual and organization in designing careers and satisfying individual aspirations.

One can argue that there is an inconsistency between the theory and practice, when it comes to the identification of competency needs. We believed that the method of identifying competency needs in terms of gaps pay attention to the demands required at a job and derive real needs while reducing managers' subjectivity in identifying managerial competency needs as some academic literature proposes (for example- Barber and Tietje, 2004; Chen et al., 2005 Hansson, 2001). However, in practice, many organizations rely on training and development requests in this regard instead of identifying real deficits in competencies (see- Ford and Noe, 1987; Guthrie and Schwoerer, 1996). In the investigation, respondents were requested to identify the current and future training and development opportunities that they wish to have to be successful in the present and near future. The results showed that majority of the training and development requests belong to the Competency Cluster 6 for the present level and Competency Cluster 5 for the future level. However, factor analysis suggested that Competency Cluster 1 of both present and future levels have the highest percentage of data variability, which is explained by that factor. Hence, findings of the study suggest that organizations have to decide what competencies should be given priority in addressing training and development requests of individual managers. Further, respondents have not requested training and development opportunities in the areas of some competency clusters for present and/or future. However, this does not mean that managers do not have needs in

the areas of those competency clusters as the results indicated that there are significant gaps in those competencies too. Therefore, a possible explanation would be that managers might have doubts on whether those could be addressed through training and development programmes. If they believe that some competencies are difficult to be assessed and developed through training and development programmes, they will not request such. Therefore, the results of this study also support the contention that training and development programmes have to be considered as one of the methods of addressing competency gaps.

Overall, the judicious management of competencies shows an orientation towards the future and could adopt a multiple constituency perspective, where a) from individuals' standpoint, they have the possibility to develop a set of competencies that could be helpful in advancing in their careers; b) from an organization's standpoint, the identification of competencies could help align HR system vertically with the organization's strategic objectives and horizontally with other HR functions such as the management of careers, c) from education and training professionals' standpoint, they could identify sound methodologies to address competency needs based on employer expectations.

Limitations and areas for future research

Identifying requisite managerial competencies that define successful managers for an organization or industrial sector is a critical process in human resource management. Competency framework should provide an operational definition for each managerial competency and sub-competency, which can be measured against observable performance standards. For the study, competencies were defined simply, as a headline plus a few sample behaviours, so competency definitions used in this study do not cater for multiple levels of detail and

mastery. Therefore, it could be argued that it is unlikely that accurate evaluation is possible. However, the way competencies will be defined will depend on how competencies will be used and the purpose of the study. Further, in the current study the level of competency is measured by using managers' self-assessment. Therefore, future studies could overcome this limitation by using other techniques to improve rater accuracy, such as standardization, or incorporating perceptions of subordinates, superiors and industry experts. Furthermore, in the study, training and development was considered as an option to address competency needs. In future studies, other options such as job enrichment, could also be investigated. All the respondents of the study worked for a single firm belongs to telecommunication sector. Therefore, the findings of the study could be generalizable to any other telecommunication service provider. Yet, one can argue that whilst the results have a specific relevance to the managers in the telecommunication industry, the findings could have a rather broader relevance. The methodology adopted in this study could be applied to conduct similar studies in any other organization or sector to identify competencies. Future studies of comparative nature could also be conducted through a larger sample across industries.

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Tables

Table 1: Population and sample

Field	Population	Sample	% represented in the sample
Finance	38	17	45
IT	32	12	38
Marketing	86	28	33
HR & Administration	76	28	37
Legal	10	7	70
Planning & Corporate Strategy	33	18	55
Operations	235	88	37
Total sample	510	198	39

Table 2: Current expertise, current importance and future importance of competencies

Competencies	Current expertise			Current importance			Future importance		
	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD
1. Customer relations knowledge	197	3.86	.81	192	4.05	1.10	190	4.62	.72
2. Cost consciousness	196	3.82	.91	191	4.09	.96	188	4.49	.75
3. Change handling skills	195	3.84	.78	189	4.24	.87	188	4.55	.74
4. Planning and scheduling	193	4.02	.77	188	4.45	.70	187	4.61	.66
5. Strategizing ability	195	3.76	.77	188	4.14	.83	186	4.51	.76
6. Technical competence	191	3.75	.82	187	4.21	.87	184	4.68	.64
7. Technology management	196	3.67	.78	191	4.01	1.01	189	4.55	.82
8. Safety focus	197	3.86	.85	192	4.13	.96	190	4.41	.82
9. Empathy with people	194	4.09	.80	189	4.13	.90	186	4.36	.80
10. Conflict resolution	194	3.73	.84	188	3.99	.99	187	4.34	.74
11. Negotiation	197	3.94	.80	190	4.35	.85	188	4.56	.75
12. Empowerment ability	196	3.91	.81	191	4.09	.95	188	4.45	.82
13. Holistic	191	3.79	.84	186	4.19	.84	184	4.45	.82
14. Creativity	194	3.77	.79	188	4.29	.81	186	4.58	.68
15. Coaching ability	192	3.78	.93	187	4.06	1.00	185	4.41	.82
16. Time management ability	197	3.88	.79	189	4.39	.78	187	4.61	.78
17. Pressure management skills	195	3.75	.76	189	4.25	.81	186	4.50	.72
18. Learning	196	3.94	.81	191	4.30	.84	188	4.59	.75
19. Listening	196	4.10	.86	190	4.31	.78	189	4.46	.74
20. Oral communication	195	3.90	.78	190	4.44	.76	190	4.54	.73
21. Written communication	193	3.97	.75	191	4.38	.73	188	4.59	.66
22. Quality focus	195	3.94	.70	189	4.40	.74	189	4.65	.61
23. Flexibility	196	4.18	.85	191	4.36	.77	189	4.59	.70
24. Team player	197	4.19	.77	190	4.43	.79	189	4.62	.72
25. Customer focus	194	3.89	.86	188	4.06	1.02	186	4.56	.79
26. Resiliency	195	3.98	.80	186	4.32	.87	185	4.59	.64
27. Ethical	195	4.03	.80	191	4.20	.90	188	4.47	.85
28. Achievement orientation	194	3.90	.83	189	4.38	.70	187	4.64	.62
29. Risk taking	197	3.79	.83	192	4.07	.89	189	4.39	.84
30. Positive vision	193	4.07	.84	189	4.30	.84	187	4.54	.71
31. Attitude to meet targets	194	4.28	.75	190	4.50	.72	188	4.71	.57

Table 3: Competency gaps and the results of t-test

	Current need					Future need				
	Perceived gap		Type of gap	t-test (2-tailed)		Perceived gap		Type of gap	t-test (2-tailed)	
	Mean	SD		t	Sig	Mean	SD		t	Sig
1. Customer relations knowledge	-.19	1.14	AM	-2.34	.021*	-.57	.89	N	-8.80	.000***
2. Cost consciousness	-.27	1.02	AM	-3.69	.000***	-.40	.80	AM	-6.88	.000***
3. Change handling skills	-.41	.89	AM	-6.36	.000***	-.32	.60	AM	-6.48	.000***
4. Planning and scheduling	-.46	.76	AM	-8.23	.000***	-.16	.61	AM	-3.54	.000***
5. Strategizing ability	-.39	.97	AM	-5.47	.000***	-.35	.70	AM	-6.82	.000***
6. Technical competence	-.48	.94	AM	-6.92	.000***	-.48	.79	AM	-8.06	.000***
7. Technology management	-.35	1.01	AM	-4.71	.000***	-.55	.94	N	-8.03	.000***
8. Safety focus	-.27	.93	AM	-3.93	.000***	-.28	.86	AM	-4.54	.000***
9. Empathy with people	-.05	.96	AM	-0.67	.498	-.24	.76	AM	-4.23	.000***
10. Conflict resolution	-.24	1.03	AM	-3.18	.002**	-.36	.83	AM	-5.88	.000***
11. Negotiation	-.41	.87	AM	-6.40	.000***	-.21	.65	AM	-4.32	.000***
12. Empowerment ability	-.18	1.07	AM	-2.36	.019**	-.36	.82	AM	-6.00	.000***
13. Holistic	-.42	.95	AM	-6.01	.000***	-.24	.75	AM	-4.40	.000***
14. Creativity	-.54	.89	N	-8.20	.000***	-.28	.71	AM	-5.30	.000***
15. Coaching ability	-.29	1.01	AM	-3.88	.000***	-.33	.81	AM	-5.53	.000***
16. Time management ability	-.50	1.03	AM	-6.57	.000***	-.22	.75	AM	-3.88	.000***
17. Pressure management skills	-.50	1.02	AM	-6.67	.000***	-.24	.73	AM	-4.48	.000***
18. Learning	-.36	.95	AM	-5.21	.000***	-.29	.72	AM	-5.42	.000***
19. Listening	-.22	.93	AM	-3.17	.002**	-.15	.67	AM	-3.14	.002**
20. Oral communication	-.54	.84	AM	-8.74	.000***	-.11	.65	AM	-2.33	.021*
21. Written communication	-.40	.78	AM	-6.97	.000***	-.20	.70	AM	-3.85	.000***
22. Quality focus	-.47	.84	AM	-7.55	.000***	-.20	.62	AM	-5.47	.000***
23. Flexibility	-.17	.94	AM	-2.53	.012**	-.23	.75	AM	-4.14	.000***
24. Team player	-.24	.76	AM	-4.35	.000***	-.19	.73	AM	-3.57	.000***
25. Customer focus	-.18	.98	AM	-2.45	.015**	-.52	.86	N	-8.23	.000***
26. Resiliency	-.32	.89	AM	-4.83	.000***	-.28	.68	AM	-5.61	.000***
27. Ethical	-.18	.90	AM	-2.73	.007**	-.26	.83	AM	-4.28	.000***
28. Achievement orientation	-.50	.83	AM	-8.18	.000***	-.26	.54	AM	-6.52	.000***
29. Risk taking	-.30	.88	AM	-4.64	.005**	-.32	.73	AM	-4.64	.000***
30. Positive vision	-.23	.97	AM	-3.20	.002**	-.25	.71	AM	-4.71	.000***
31. Attitude to meet targets	-.23	.77	AM	-4.11	.000***	-.21	.60	AM	-4.68	.000***

Note: Type of Gap: Value ≤ -.51: negative gap (N); $-.5 \leq \text{Value} \leq .5$: adjustment margin (AM); Value ≥ .51: positive gap (P)

* p<0.05, **p<0.01, ***p<0.001. For any of the competency variable normality distribution was not violated in running the t-test.

Table 4: Results of t-test (on some selected competencies at current level)

Pair	Competencies	Perceived gap (Mean)	Type of gap	t-test (2-tailed)		
				t	df	Sig
1	Empathy with people	-.05	AM	6.44	184	.000***
	Creativity	-.54	N			
2	Customer relations knowledge	-.19	AM	3.00	186	.003**
	Technical competence	-.48	AM			
3	Technical competence	-.48	AM	-5.24	183	.000***
	Empathy with people	-.05	AM			
4	Achievement orientation	-.50	AM	-3.83	187	.000***
	Flexibility	-.17	AM			
5	Achievement orientation	-.50	AM	-5.79	187	.000***
	Empathy with people	-.05	AM			
6	Customer relations knowledge	-.19	AM	3.72	187	.000***
	Creativity	-.54	N			
7	Negotiation	-.41	AM	1.31	184	.189
	Coaching ability	-.29	AM			

Note: **p<0.01; ***p<0.001

For any of the competency variable normality distribution was not violated in running the t-test.

Table 5: Factor analysis for current competency needs

	Managerial Competency Clusters					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
Customer relations knowledge	.478					
Achievement orientation	.538					
Attitude to meet targets	.672					
Change handling skills	.446					
Cost consciousness	.619					
Empowerment ability	.648					
Quality focus	.405					
Team player	.583					
Customer focus	.600					
Holistic		.464				
Creativity		.639				
Negotiation		.450				
Risk taking		.582				
Learning		.763				
Strategizing ability		.625				
Time management ability		.459				
Conflict resolution			.668			
Coaching ability			.461			
Positive vision			.579			
Pressure management skills			.752			
Resiliency			.660			
Oral communication				.653		
Planning and scheduling				.423		
Written communication				.754		
Empathy with people					.653	
Flexibility					.469	
Listening					.509	
Ethical					.498	
Technical competence						.516
Safety focus						.458
Technology management						.739
Percentage of variance	43.96	4.71	4.03	3.70	3.47	3.38
Cronbach's Alpha based on standardized items	.877	.869	.819	.712	.751	.723

Table 6: Factor analysis for future competency needs

	Managerial Competency Clusters							
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Empathy with people	.499							
Empowerment ability	.745							
Holistic	.700							
Creativity	.459							
Negotiation	.518							
Pressure management skills	.508							
Quality focus		.631						
Risk taking		.545						
Learning		.732						
Strategizing ability		.670						
Team player		.408						
Achievement orientation			.736					
Change handling skills			.563					
Flexibility			.561					
Planning and scheduling			.671					
Listening				.666				
Oral communication				.744				
Ethical				.452				
Technical competence					.466			
Positive vision					.784			
Safety focus					.505			
Technology management					.701			
Customer relations knowledge						.682		
Cost consciousness						.571		
Customer focus						.578		
Written communication						.552		
Coaching ability							.641	
Resiliency							.770	
Time management ability							.518	
Attitude to meet targets								.497
Conflict resolution								.494
Percentage of variance	29.11	7.57	6.13	5.03	4.31	4.08	3.75	3.64
Cronbach's Alpha based on standardized items	.794	.741	.738	.711	.720	.699	.714	.689

Table 7: Training and development requests

Present	Future		Total
	No	Yes	
No	15	17	32
Yes	9	145	154
Total	24	162	186

McNemar test (N=186)	
Chi-square	1.885
Asymp. Sig	.170
Exact Sig. (1-tailed)	.084

Note: $p > 0.05$

Table 8: Areas in which training and development opportunities are requested

For present					For future				
		Competency Cluster	N	%			Competency Cluster	N	%
1	Technical competence	6	206	42	1	Technical competence	5	126	34
2	Communication and presentation skills	4 & 5	86	18	2	Communication and presentation skills	4 & 6	77	21
3	Empathy with people	5	47	10	3	Empathy with people	1	60	16
4	Change handling skills	1	32	7	4	Technology management	5	36	10
5	Strategizing ability	2	28	6	5	Holistic	1	17	5
6	Customer relations knowledge	1	26	5	6	Change handling skills	3	13	3
7	Holistic	2	21	4	7	Customer relations knowledge	6	12	3
8	Negotiation	2	13	3	8	Cost consciousness	6	8	2
9	Quality focus	1	11	2	8	Negotiation	1	8	2
10	Technology management	6	10	2	8	Quality focus	2	8	2
11	Cost consciousness	1	9	1	11	Strategizing ability	2	7	2
Total requests			489	100	Total requests			372	100

Note: Communication and presentation skills were considered to be represented by listening, oral and written communication